

EFFECTS OF SURFACE TREATMENT ON MECHANICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF GLASS-FLAKE REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES

W R Broughton, M J Lodeiro and G D Pilkington
National Physical Laboratory
Teddington, Middlesex, TW11 0LW, UK
bill.broughton@npl.co.uk

SUMMARY

This paper presents the results of a study evaluating the effects of aminosilane and titanate surface treatments on mechanical and thermal properties of glass-flake reinforced polypropylene. The role of the interface is shown to be key in determining the tensile and flexural properties, impact resistance, thermal expansion and residual stress distribution in these materials.

Keywords: glass-flake, interface, mechanical and thermal properties, polypropylene, residual stress, surface treatment

INTRODUCTION

The incorporation of glass flakes into coatings and plastics offers significant performance advantages compared with many other forms of reinforcement, and hence the increasing use of glass-flake reinforced materials for high performance engineering and commodity products. In contrast to the anisotropy associated with conventional linear glass fibre reinforcement, glass-flake reinforced polymer composites exhibit in-plane isotropic properties. Property enhancement includes reduced warpage and shrinkage, improved dimensional stability, surface hardness and wear resistance, and increased tensile and flexural stiffness. Glass-flake reinforced products also display good resistance to weathering and chemical attack. This paper presents a study evaluating the effects of aminosilane and titanate surface treatment on the mechanical and thermal properties of glass-flake reinforced polypropylene and compares the results with pure polypropylene and untreated glass-flake reinforced polypropylene. The role of the interface is shown to be key in determining the tensile and flexural properties, impact resistance and residual stresses in these materials. An improvement in interfacial adhesion is shown to enhance stiffness and strength, and reduce residual stresses. This was coupled with a reduction in matrix ductility and impact resistance. A number of residual stress measurement techniques including layer-removal, incremental slitting and dilatometry (thermal expansion hysteresis curves), along with ultrasonic time-of-flight/velocity measurements are shown to be useful in determining the effects of surface treatments on interfacial bonding of these composite materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The composite materials used in this study consisted of Novatec[®] PP BC06C polypropylene reinforced with Microglas[®] glass flakes that were either untreated, or modified with aminosilane (0.05 wt% and 0.28 wt%) or titanate (0.09 wt% and 0.42 wt%) coupling agent. Un-reinforced polypropylene was also evaluated. The materials were in the form of injection-molded plaques (150 mm x 150 mm) with a nominal thickness of 3 mm that were provided by NGF Europe Limited. The mold temperature was 230 °C. The polypropylene had a density of 905 kg/m³ and the glass flake content for the composite materials was nominally 30.0 wt%. Volume fraction, V_f , weight fraction, W_f , and density, ρ , for all materials (see Table 1) were measured in accordance with international (ISO) standards ISO 1172 [1] and ISO 1183 [2].

Table 1 Density, fibre volume fractions and fibre weight fractions

Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Volume Fraction (%)	Weight Fraction (%)
Polypropylene	905 ± 1	-	-
Untreated	1,126 ± 1	13.33 ± 0.06	30.29 ± 0.05
<u>Aminosilane</u>			
0.05%	1,115 ± 1	13.50 ± 0.10	30.68 ± 0.09
0.28%	1,121 ± 1	12.73 ± 0.06	29.22 ± 0.13
<u>Titanate</u>			
0.09%	1,129 ± 1	12.70 ± 0.10	29.13 ± 0.15
0.42%	1,117 ± 1	13.13 ± 0.12	29.98 ± 0.25

The effective length (width) and thickness of the glass flakes were $73.8 \pm 7.8 \mu\text{m}$ and $7.4 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. Optical micrographs of the glass flakes obtained from the central region of the plaque in the direction parallel to the mold flow are shown in Figure 1. Figure 1a shows the top surface (plan view) and Figure 1b shows the through-thickness flake orientation (side view). Scanning electron micrographs of typical fracture surfaces near the surface and core are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1 Glass flake orientation: plan view (left) and side view (right)

Figure 2 SEM images of flake orientation in the skin (left) and core (right) layers

Mechanical and Thermal Properties

A series of tensile, flexure and impact tests were conducted under standard laboratory conditions (23 ± 2 °C, $50 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity) on the polypropylene and glass-flake reinforced polypropylene materials to determine the effect of surface treatments on the mechanical performance. A minimum of five specimens was tested for each loading mode and orientation. The tensile tests were conducted on small dumbbell specimens (Type 1BA) in accordance with ISO 527-2 [3] at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min using an Instron 5500 tension-compression test frame. Tensile modulus, Poisson's ratio and tensile strength were measured parallel to the flow direction (i.e. longitudinal direction). Contact extensometers were used to measure the longitudinal and transverse (i.e. across the flow direction) strains. Four-point flexure tests were conducted on rectangular specimens (80 mm x 10 mm) according to ISO 14125 [4] at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. The inner and outer flexure spans were 16 mm and 48 mm, respectively. The loading rollers were 5 mm in diameter. Drop weight impact tests were conducted in accordance with ISO 6603-2 [5] on all five composite materials using a Rosand Drop Weight (IFW5) machine. The drop height was set to 0.25 m to produce an impact velocity of 2.22 m/s. The drop energy was 5.11 J. A 20 mm diameter hemispherical indenter was used. The panels (150 mm x 150 mm x 3 mm) were simply supported. Peak energy, total energy and peak force were measured.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to determine the melt-crystallization and crystalline content of the polypropylene and composite materials. Measurements were undertaken using a TA Instruments DSC Q2000 at 20 °C/min heating rate according to ISO 11357-3 [6]. Crystalline content was also determined using X-ray diffraction (XRD), a volumetric method (based on density) and Raman spectroscopy. Glass transition temperature, T_g , was determined using dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) using a TA Instruments DMA 2980 at a frequency of 1 Hz and a heating rate of 3 °C/min in the single cantilever-bending mode in accordance with ISO 6721-11 [7].

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in the longitudinal direction was measured using mechanical dilatometry. Tests were conducted on rectangular bar specimens (40 mm x 10 mm) in accordance with ASTM E 289 [8]. The test specimens were initially cooled to -80 °C to settle the system and then heated to about 120 °C. Thermal cycling was repeated until the strains versus temperature curves were almost identical (usually three cycles).

The layer-removal and incremental slitting methods [9-14] were used to measure residual stress and strain distributions in the polymeric materials. The layer removal method involved measuring the curvature of specimens (80 mm x 10 mm) following the progressive removal of thin layers of uniform thickness (~0.1 mm) from the surface. In response to removal of a layer the sample restores equilibrium by warping to a shape, which closely resembles a circular arc. The measured curvature as a function of the depth removed was used to calculate the stress distribution through the thickness of the material prior to layer removal. Measurements were taken 5 minutes after the layer was removed. Arc height was measured using a Mitutoyo laser scan micrometer LSM-301 (resolution of 100 μm) and then the curvature was calculated.

The incremental slitting method involved cutting a slit (1 mm wide) of progressively increasing depth into rectangular specimens (50 mm x 25 mm) to release the stresses along the plane of the cut and measuring the resultant longitudinal strain on the back surface of the specimen. A strain gauge was bonded to the specimen surface for this purpose. The notch depth was increased in 0.1 mm increments. The resultant strain was measured within 2 minutes after slitting. The process was repeated until the specimen was almost fully dissected. Strain data was collected using a National Instrument Compact DAQ unit (NI 9172 chassis and NI 9237 strain card).

Ultrasonic time of flight/velocity was used to determine the effectiveness of the interfacial adhesion between the glass flakes and polypropylene matrix. The basis of the technique is the measurement of the apparent velocity of ultrasonic compression waves in the sample by comparison of reference positions in the waveform with and without the sample. Assuming no change in frequency content occurs during transmission of the ultrasonic signal through the sample. The transmitting and receiving transducers were attached directly to the opposing faces of the sample with the aid of a coupling medium (thin layer of propylene glycol). Measurements were conducted on three samples for each material using 1 MHz transducers. Initial measurements were carried out on the polypropylene and composites at room temperature to obtain baseline values. Further measurements were carried out under ambient conditions, on the polymeric materials, following exposure to sub-zero temperatures. The specimens were exposed to decreasing temperatures in 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ steps from ambient to -150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Between each step the specimen was returned to room temperature and the specimen temperature allowed to equilibrate with the temperature of the surrounding environment (typically 30 minutes). The soak time at the conditioning temperatures was 30 minutes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The composite materials showed noticeable differences in mechanical properties for the different surface treatments with the aminosilanes proving more effective in promoting interfacial bonding (i.e. higher stiffness and strength) compared with the titanate treatments. Tables 2 to 4 show the tensile, flexure and impact data measured for the polypropylene and glass-flake reinforced polypropylene materials. The aminosilane 0.28% treatment gives the highest values of tensile stiffness and strength and 0.42% titanate the lowest values. As a consequence of improving the interfacial adhesion strength, the impact resistance (total energy absorbed) and ductility of the composite decreases. This is to be expected as higher stiffness and strength is associated with a reduction in fracture toughness, and vice-versa.

It is worth noting that the addition of the glass flakes without any surface treatment enhances the stiffness of the polypropylene. The presence of glass flakes in the polypropylene, however, causes a reduction in strength, although the effect is minimal for the aminosilane treatments. The longitudinal flexural properties are slightly higher than those measured in the transverse direction indicating a slight in-plane anisotropy.

Table 2 Tensile properties of neat resin and composite materials

Material	Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Strength (MPa)	Failure Strain (%)
Polypropylene	1.89 ± 0.04	0.39 ± 0.02	31.4 ± 0.3	18.7 ± 6.7
Untreated	4.20 ± 0.09	0.32 ± 0.02	24.4 ± 0.4	2.04 ± 0.41
<u>Aminosilane</u>				
0.05%	4.77 ± 0.23	0.28 ± 0.01	28.9 ± 1.0	1.40 ± 0.19
0.28%	4.91 ± 0.29	0.31 ± 0.01	29.4 ± 1.0	1.22 ± 0.16
<u>Titanate</u>				
0.09%	4.67 ± 0.16	0.31 ± 0.02	24.3 ± 0.9	1.68 ± 0.17
0.42%	4.05 ± 0.45	0.30 ± 0.04	23.4 ± 0.3	2.01 ± 0.46

Table 3 Flexural properties of neat resin and composite materials

Material	Modulus (GPa)		Strength (MPa)	
	Longitudinal	Transverse	Longitudinal	Transverse
Polypropylene	1.91 ± 0.05	1.94 ± 0.07	42.36 ± 0.28	44.84 ± 0.13
Untreated	3.39 ± 0.09	3.21 ± 0.06	44.11 ± 0.20	43.32 ± 0.45
<u>Aminosilane</u>				
0.05%	4.34 ± 0.17	4.13 ± 0.09	55.31 ± 3.02	53.50 ± 0.31
0.28%	4.30 ± 0.03	4.05 ± 0.16	56.12 ± 1.03	53.91 ± 0.57
<u>Titanate</u>				
0.09%	3.28 ± 0.09	3.27 ± 0.16	44.47 ± 3.73	43.46 ± 0.59
0.42%	3.04 ± 0.22	3.05 ± 0.11	41.57 ± 0.62	40.51 ± 0.62

Table 4 Impact properties of composite materials

Material	Peak Energy (Joules)	Total Energy (Joules)	Peak Force (N)
Untreated	0.73 ± 0.15	3.08 ± 0.29	265 ± 35
<u>Aminosilane</u>			
0.05%	0.74 ± 0.15	2.52 ± 0.53	296 ± 24
0.28%	0.60 ± 0.07	2.51 ± 0.13	263 ± 22
<u>Titanate</u>			
0.09%	0.81 ± 0.11	3.06 ± 0.31	304 ± 11
0.42%	0.75 ± 0.10	2.86 ± 0.44	257 ± 58

The melt-crystallization of the polypropylene seems to be unaffected by the presence of untreated or modified glass flakes. The peak temperature of crystallization, T_c , and peak temperature of crystallization melt, T_m , as shown in Table 5, were approximately 130 °C and 163 °C, respectively. Differences in T_g (see Table 5) obtained for all six materials were minimal with T_g having a value of ~12 °C. Onset temperatures for melting and crystallization were approximately 132 °C and 153 °C, respectively.

Table 5 Glass transition, crystallization and melting temperatures

Material	T_g (°C)	T_c (°C)	T_m (°C)
Polypropylene	11.0	130.4	162.3
Untreated	11.7	130.0	163.4
<u>Aminosilane</u>			
0.05%	11.3	129.6	163.0
0.28%	12.1	129.5	163.6
<u>Titanate</u>			
0.09%	12.3	129.8	163.7
0.42%	12.1	127.6	164.1

The values of crystalline volume content determined for the different materials using the four techniques are shown in Table 6. Considering the differences the crystallinity data obtained for the four techniques are in reasonable agreement. There is no clear evidence to suggest that the presence of untreated or modified glass flakes have affected the crystallinity of the polypropylene.

Table 6 Crystalline volume content (%) measurements

Material	Volumetric	DSC	XRD	Raman Spectroscopy
Polypropylene	61.61	56.26	56.30	63.40
Untreated	59.07	58.09	62.70	58.10
<u>Aminosilane</u>				
0.05%	58.54	55.70	62.36	65.10
0.28%	59.64	55.21	56.70	58.60
<u>Titanate</u>				
0.09%	58.47	56.63	48.48	55.60
0.42%	56.90	55.20	51.90	54.00

There is no clear evidence that any particular surface treatment has a noticeable affect on the CTE (see Table 7). Thermal expansion hysteresis occurs following cooling from 120 °C on the first thermal cycle (Figure 3). This can be attributed primarily to process induced residual stresses within the material. The size of the thermal strain hysteresis loop was dependent on the type and level of coupling agent employed.

Thermal strain hysteresis for the aminosilane treatments are noticeably less than for the untreated and titanate treatments, indicating that the latter are less effective in promoting interfacial adhesion (i.e. load transfer from the polypropylene matrix to the glass flakes is reduced).

Table 7 Coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of neat resin and composites

Material	CTE ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Strain Difference (%)
Polypropylene	67	0.31
Untreated	45	0.35
Aminosilane		
0.05%	39	0.11
0.28%	40	0.14
Titanate		
0.09%	48	0.35
0.42%	41	0.25

Figure 3 Strain vs. temperature curves for 0.05% aminosilane and 0.09% titanate

There were distinct differences in residual stress distributions (see Figure 4) for the various polymeric materials with the aminosilane treatments exhibiting lower surface compressive and core tensile stresses than the titanate and untreated materials. The maximum tensile residual stresses at the core for all the polymeric materials ranged between 2 and 3 MPa with the core tensile region extending further towards the surface for the untreated and titanate treatments. The untreated and titanate treated materials have similar residual stress profiles. The compressive stresses at the surface of the polypropylene and aminosilane treated materials were about 3 MPa similar to the neat resin, whereas the compressive stresses for the untreated and titanate treatments ranged between 20 to 40 MPa. The residual stress measurements represent the state of stress in aged material (one year old), thus residual stresses can be expected to have relaxed considerably since manufacture. The residual strain distributions determined using the incremental slitting method mirrored the thermal expansion hysteresis and layer removal data (see Figure 5).

Figure 4 Residual stress distributions obtained using layer removal method

Figure 5 Residual strain distributions obtained using incremental slitting method

The “apparent” ultrasonic velocity decreased (i.e. transit time increased) with increasing exposure at sub-zero temperatures for the untreated and titanate samples, whereas no changes were observed for polypropylene and aminosilane samples (see Figure 6). The increase in transit time may be due to an increase in signal path length or a change in frequency content of the waveform caused by interfacial damage (i.e. formation of air gaps at interfaces) or a change in material stiffness through the loss of interfacial integrity.

Figure 6 Ultrasonic velocity for unconditioned and -150 °C conditioned materials

CONCLUSIONS

The results clearly show that the tensile and flexural stiffness and strength, impact resistance and residual stresses of the glass-flake reinforced polypropylene composites depend strongly on the type and level of coupling agent employed. This was associated with a reduction in matrix ductility and impact resistance. The influence of coupling agents on the melt-crystallization and crystalline content of the polypropylene, however, was found to be minimal for the aminosilane and titanate treatments. Glass flakes modified with aminosilane gave higher stiffness and strengths than the titanate treatments. The inclusion of the glass flakes without any surface treatment enhances the stiffness of the polypropylene. Residual stresses and thermal expansion hysteresis were highest for the untreated material and lowest for 0.05% aminosilane. Thermal expansion hysteresis provided an indication of the relative levels of residual stresses in the polymeric materials, which was verified using the layer removal method for determining residual stress distributions. The present study also shows that ultrasonic velocity measurements conducted on composite materials before and after exposure to sub-zero temperatures provides a quick method of evaluating the effectiveness of a surface treatment in promoting interfacial adhesion.

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